

Prototypes of alternative storage backends

Milestone M7

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Lead Beneficiary:

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ), Julian Kunkel, Jakob Lüttgau

Other contributing authors:

Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC), Sandro Fiore, Alesandro D'Anca
The University of Reading (UREAD), Bryan Lawrence, Julian Kunkel
Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Neil Massey
Seagate Systems UK Limited (SEAGATE), Huang Hua

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Means of verifications: Source code for the prototype has been produced and preliminary functionality tests have been executed.

The source code is available in open source license in two repositories on Github:

<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

<https://github.com/cedadev/S3-netcdf-python/tree/0.2>

Achieved: Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date: Does not apply.

Comments: This document provides some information about the implementation.

Prototypes of alternative storage backend

Summary

The objectives of the Exploitability work package within ESIWACE include two objectives:

- (1) The development of a new way of laying data onto storage which provides performance without compromising the familiar NetCDF interface.
- (2) The development of a prototype tape library.

We are delivering these two objectives using the same basic philosophy, which is to develop middleware which is easily deployable by users and system administrators, and which utilises fragmentation to provide performance. The current design includes the same basic concepts in two different software packages (the “Earth System Data Middleware” and the “Semantic Storage Layer”) which target these two objectives. Future projects may merge some or all the underlying functionality. This milestone (7) reports a staging point in the development of these two components, the release of tagged software for the ESDM and SemSL.

Context

The figure indicates how milestone 7 fits in the development plan. The pre-ESIWACE methodology is shown in the first column, applications write through a stack to filesystems. In the second column the key ESIWACE software capabilities of milestone 7 are shown: the top section shows applications utilising the ESDM to write to both files and objects; the lower section shows applications utilising the SemSL interface to write NetCDF files to either file systems or object storage. Milestone 8 will introduce support for tape libraries. Milestone 9 will be a deployment milestone.

No performance data is included here, as scale testing for alternative backends requires hardware setups that are not yet available. Performance at scale for the POSIX backend is very good (Kunkel et al, 2018, “Towards Exploiting Data Locality with the Earth-System Data Middleware”, in review).

Part One – Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM)

Concepts and Status

The ESDM middleware has been designed to allow interactions with different kinds of backends, by means of data storage and retrieval. Specifically, the ESDM middleware allows interactions with various backends, exploiting different specific plugins to enable connection and I/O operations on different storage types. These plugins are embedded into a pre-existing and generic core module to support and expose all the interfaces needed to define I/O operations on the different backends; each specific plugin implements the interfaces to allow data management, storage, access and retrieval.

Milestone 7 reports the delivery of design and software plugins to support the DDN WOS object storage and Seagate's Mero storage via the Clovis API. This software is checked into a public github repository at <https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>.

Prototype of interface development for WOS: wrapper library

The ESDM middleware exposes interfaces for the management of I/O operations on different storage backends to support the set of CRUD functionalities.

The DDN WOS backend is a specific ESDM plugin which has been developed in order to define: i) the structures needed to hold all the information required for the WOS management; ii) the routines to enable and check the backend remote connection, and; iii) the functions to allow read/write operations on the WOS storage.

DDN provides APIs for interaction with the WOS cluster in the C++, Java and Python programming languages. The ESDM middleware has been developed in C code. Further development activity has therefore been necessary to fill the gap between the programming languages used for the implementation of the middleware and the API provided by WOS. In more detail, a C library that represents a wrapper for C++ WOS APIs has been developed.

The newly developed library implements the following interfaces:

C interface	WOS library API	Description
Conn(char *host)	WosCluster::Connect(host)	Connect to the WOS cluster
GetPolicy(t_WosClusterPtr * wos, char *wpolicy)	wos->GetPolicy(wpolicy)	Check and get the WOS policy
WosObjCreate()	WosObj::Create()	Create a WOS object
SetDataObj(const void *, int, t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj->SetData(data, len)	Set the data buffer to store in a WOS object
SetMetaObj(const char *, const	wobj->SetMeta("<key>",	Set the metadata (key, value)

char *, t_WosObjPtr *)	"value");	associated with the WOS object
Put_b(t_WosStatus *, t_WosOID *, t_WosPolicy *, t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Put(status, oid, policy, wobj);	Store the wos object in the WOS cluster (blocking form)
Put_nb(t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosPolicy *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Put(wobj, policy, callback, context)	Store the WOS object in the WOS cluster (non blocking form)
Get_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Get(status, oid, wobj);	Get the WOS object from the WOS cluster (blocking form)
Get_nb(const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Get(oid, callback, context)	Get the WOS object from the WOS cluster (non blocking form)
GetDataObj(const void **, int *, const t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj->GetData(data, length)	Get the data buffer from the WOS object
GetMetaObj(const char *, char **, const t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj->GetMeta("<key>", value)	Get metadata from the WOS object (key, value)
Delete_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Delete(status, oid)	Delete the WOS object (blocking form)
Delete_nb(const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Delete(oid, callback, context)	Delete the WOS object (non blocking form)
Exists_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Exists(status, oid)	Check the existence of a WOS object using its OID (blocking form)
Exists_nb(const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Exists(oid, callback, context)	Check the existence of a WOS object using its OID (non blocking form)
Reserve_b(t_WosStatus *, t_WosOID *, t_WosPolicy *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Reserve(status, oid, policy)	Reserve an OID to be used in the next PutOID call (blocking form)
Reserve_nb(t_WosPolicy *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->Reserve(policy, callback, context)	Reserve an OID to be used in the next PutOID call (non blocking form)
PutOID_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->PutOID(status, oid, wobj)	Put a WOS object using the reserved oid (blocking form)
PutOID_nb(t_WosObjPtr *, const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos->PutOID(wobj, oid, callback, context)	Put a WOS object using the reserved oid (non blocking form)

In addition, the following C structures have been developed to wrap the related C++ objects:

C Struct	C++ Object	Description
t_WosClusterPtr	WosClusterPtr	Pointer to the WOS Cluster
t_WosStatus	WosStatus	Status value returned by each call
t_WosOID	WosOID	WOS object identifier
t_WosPolicy	WosPolicy	WOS policy
t_WosObjPtr	WosObjPtr	Pointer to a WOS object

ESDM interface for WOS object storage

The new wrapper library has been used for the low-level definition of the interfaces to the WOS storage backend. The ESDM interfaces to the WOS object storage were then implemented using C functions to allow the connection, storage and retrieval of WOS objects.

In more detail, the prototype is based on a set of routines and structures that implement the following functionalities:

- (1) registration of the modules needed for the management of the WOS cluster;
- (2) connection to the WOS cluster;
- (3) execution of write and read operations;
- (4) finalisation of the management modules.

The registration phase initialises all the structures defined for the management of the WOS backend, i.e. the necessary configuration variables and callbacks to allow the I/O operations.

The connection phase exploits these structures, enabling and checking the connection to the target WOS cluster. In this phase, the information regarding the IP address of the WOS target host and the needed policy are used.

The process of writing a fragment on the WOS storage exploits two routines to diversify the allocation of the required resources on the WOS backend and the actual storage of information (data and metadata) contained in the data buffer:

- (1) the alloc routine creates a pool of WOS objects (one in the first prototype) able to hold the data contained in the data buffer to be stored;
- (2) the write function stores the data contained in the data buffer into the aforementioned WOS objects.

The read phase of a previously stored data buffer exploits the WOS functions to retrieve the related WOS objects and the data contained therein.

The finalisation phase deallocates the resources used in the previous phases.

The following table shows in detail the correspondence between the developed functions and the related WOS API.

Function	ESDM-WOS interface	WOS C API
Init Connect	esdm_backend_wos_init	wos_cluster = Conn(host) GetPolicy(ebm->wos_cluster, policy)
Open	esdm_backend_wos_open	oid = CreateWoid()
Write	esdm_backend_wos_alloc	Reserve_b(wos_status, ebm->oid_list[i], ebm->wos_policy, ebm->wos_cluster);
	esdm_backend_wos_write	wobj = WosObjCreate(); SetDataObj(buffer, ebm->size_list[i], wobj); PutOID_b(wos_status, ebm->oid_list[i], wobj, ebm->wos_cluster);
Read	esdm_backend_wos_read	Get_b(wos_status, (t_WosOID *) obj_handle, wobj, ebm->wos_cluster) GetDataObj(&buffer, &len, wobj)
Finalize	esdm_backend_wos_close	DeleteWosWoid((t_WosOID *) obj_handle)

In the prototype, the aforementioned interfaces are used by the ESDM core component by means of two predefined APIs, `fragment_update` and `fragment_retrieve`, which collect all the operations necessary for writing and reading an ESDM fragment.

These APIs are mapped to the corresponding I/O management functions on WOS objects: `esdm_backend_wos_fragment_update` and `esdm_backend_wos_fragment_retrieve`. In detail, the update phase exploits the `wos_alloc`, `wos_open`, `wos_write` and `wos_close` functions in order to initialise a WOS object, store the data contained in the data buffer and deallocate the used resources. The retrieve phase, on the other hand, uses the `wos_open`, `wos_read` and `wos_close` functions in order to retrieve data from a WOS object and to deallocate the used resources.

In order to check the correct execution of the library and related interfaces, the WOS module has been plugged into the embedded ESDM test application (runnable by typing `make test`) by configuring ESDM as follows

```
./configure --enable-wos=/path/to/distlib --with-boost=/path/to/boostlib
```

where the libraries “dist” and “boost” implement the interface to DDN WOS service, and by adding the following description to the backend list in `esdm.conf`:

```
{ "type": "WOS", "name": "w1", "target": "host=192.168.80.33;policy=test;" }
```

Here, it is assumed that the WOS server is running over a VM with IP address 192.168.80.33 and the policy “test” is available for the test. The test has been successful.

Finally, the interface to the performance model named “generic-perf-model” has been added to the WOS plugin. This simple model, provided by the ESDM platform, estimates the time to transfer data from/to the WOS server based on the data size, as follows.

$time = size / Throughput + Latency$

In this prototype, the model assumes that the parameters “Throughput” and “Latency” are constant. They can be set in esdm.conf as in the following example:

```
{ "type": "WOS", "name": "w1", "target": "host=192.168.80.33;policy=test;", "performance-model" : {"latency" : 0.000001, "throughput" : 500.0} }
```

ESDM interface for Mero via Clovis

Clovis is the interface exported by Mero for use by the Mero applications. In this project, ESDM uses Clovis interfaces to access a Mero storage cluster.

Clovis is divided into the following sub-interfaces:

- (1) access sub-interface, which provides basic abstraction to build storage application;
- (2) management sub-interface, which provides methods for Mero cluster: deployment, configuration, re-configuration and monitoring;
- (3) extension sub-interface, which allows applications to extend Mero functionality without modifying the core Mero.

Currently, the Clovis interfaces are written in the C language.

Similarly to WOS, functionality to access data on Mero has been implemented covering:

- Parsing configuration file to initialise the backend. To access a Mero storage cluster, Clovis applications need a list of parameters, such as the confd service network address, the client network address, the profile ID and process ID in configuration. These parameters are stored in a configuration file, as part of the backend information. Clovis backend parses the configuration and passes them to the Clovis initialisation interfaces.
- Connecting to Mero storage service with Clovis APIs. After the Clovis client instance has been initialised properly, the Clovis backend connects to the specified Mero storage cluster and fetches some key information to further initialise the client.
- The following dataspace/dataset operations are now supported:
 - Alloc: A new object is allocated in Mero to accommodate dataset/dataspace. A globally unique object ID is generated and selected for the new object, and object ID and along with some useful metadata are returned back to ESDM if this operation is successful.
 - Open: Open an Mero object for read/write. While successfully opened, an opaque handle is returned for further access in read/write routines. This handle should be closed with the close() operation. All allocated resources will be freed. This handle should no longer be used.
 - Read/Write: Mero objects can be read from and/or written to, with properly opened handle. Data can be read from and/or written to a specified location, with specified size. For read, a buffer to hold the returned data will be allocated within here, and should be freed after use by ESDM.
 - Close: When read/write operation has completed and object is no longer used, object should be close()-d.

- Fragment Retrieve/Update interfaces. Fragment update and retrieve are considered to be atomic operations in ESDM. These operations are implemented with the aforementioned operations. A fragment is identified by its container name, its dimensions and position. This information is used to form a unique fragment name. For every fragment, a new Mero object is allocated and associated with. The mapping from a fragment to Mero object is managed and maintained. Operations on the fragment comprise open(), read() and write(), and finally close().
- Clovis backend finalisation. When all ESDM operations have completed, the Clovis backend finalisation interface should be called to disconnect from Mero storage services, de-allocate all resources, and etc.
- A test utility is introduced to cover the above functionalities. The test utility is going to simulate ESDM access pattern and conduct operations with the above interfaces.

A performance test of Mero via the existing benchmark tool is pending.

Part Two – The Semantic Storage Layer (SemSL)

Concepts and Status

Like the ESDM, the semantic storage layer (SemSL) has been designed to allow users to read and write fragments of data onto storage systems with differing backends. There are two significant differences from the ESDM however, firstly, the SemSL fragments NetCDF files into NetCDF files, whereas the ESDM fragments data into ESDM native fragments, secondly, the SemSL is only available in Python, whereas the ESDM is available to any interface which binds to an ESDM equipped HDF library.

The SemSL exists to meet two needs – to prototype semantic concepts and methods which could eventually be absorbed into the ESDM, and to provide a test harness for alternative backends which include tape – so that we can meet the ESIWACE requirement to build new tape library interfaces. It is also slated to support elements of workflow handling for the demonstrators.

Milestone 7 reports the delivery of the initial proof of concept prototype, which has been tested fragmenting NetCDF files into NetCDF files which can be stored both on existing file systems and on object stores. The software is available on a public GitHub repository at <https://github.com/cedadev/S3-netcdf-python/tree/0.2>. The upcoming Milestone 8 will address the integration with tape.

Semantic Storage Layer Architecture

The SemSL is delivered by specialising an existing high-level interface. The current version supports only python and specialises netcdf4-python to provide s3netcdf-python. Calls to s3netcdf-python are either routed to the normal netcdf4-python library or the customised library depending on whether the user has opened a specialised NetCDF4 file or a normal file.

The full details of how the customised library handles fragmentation and aggregation in the aggregation layer appear are beyond the scope of this document and will appear in a paper that is being prepared for the research literature. Here we summarise the key aspects:

1. The *Library Support* layer handles memory management, mapping data from the native library into forms suitable for aggregation (or vice versa, during read). This mapping supports datasets which are larger than the available memory.
2. The *Aggregation* layer handles the splitting into, or aggregating from, subarray files. A key concept of aggregation is the master-array which describes the set of subarray fragments. Subarrays are valid NetCDF files which conform to the CFA conventions (see below). During writes this component will utilise an array splitter to determine optimal fragment size given storage parameters and the data dimensionality.
3. At this point there are valid NetCDF files being written or read, but they may be coming from or going to a variety of different backends. This process is a candidate for optimisation via parallelisation and keep-alive connections. While this prototype does have a branch with some parallelisation, for proof-of-concept we have concentrated on the serial version. The next refactoring will address parallelisation and performance.
4. Whether reading or writing, it may be desirable to cache to local disk, particularly when the target has high latency and/or the process is asynchronous. This caching will be mandatory for the master-array and may also be useful for the subarrays.
5. The fragment files must then be moved to and from storage, using standard protocols – although specific plugins will be necessary for specific storage targets. The prototype includes support for both standard POSIX files and objects accessible via the S3 object store interface.

Aggregation

The Climate-Forecast Aggregation (CFA) encoding in NetCDF (URL) is used in the prototype to describe the master and subarrays. The master data array describes a hyper-rectangular matrix of partitions. This partition matrix, in effect, indicates the position in the master data array that each subarray occupies.

The master data array is itself a valid NetCDF file, with all the relevant metadata, but the payload describes the partition matrix, and so it is very small, and will be a candidate for remaining on local disk, if not in memory. The master data array can be reconstructed from the subarray files, even if the master data array has been lost/corrupted, as the position of each subarray in the master data array is known from the dimension variables in the subarray. The subarray location is identified by a URI string in the master array. This allows individual subarrays to be on different storage types.

The current prototype has only been tested with all subarray files on disk, or all in an object store, but hybrid distributions will be supported in a future version.

Next Steps for the SemSL

Following this release, the software is being refactored, concentrating on performance and preparing for adding tape backends.